

THE USE OF ELECTRONIC DICTIONARY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

The use of computer technology occupies an important place in teaching a foreign language to a modern student. One of the means of teaching using computer technology is the use of electronic dictionaries. Electronic dictionary is a new word in the history of lexicography. Currently, electronic dictionaries are superior to paper dictionaries and are becoming independent teaching aids. Electronic dictionaries have a number of obvious and significant advantages over traditional dictionaries. Among special linguistic dictionaries, various phraseological dictionaries are of great interest.

The article describes the structure and distinctive features of the electronic version of the "German-Russian and Russian-German Dictionary of Phraseological Units and Set Phrases" by B.P. Shekasyuk in foreign language classes at the university.

The relevance of the study is due to the fact that the need to introduce new educational technologies becomes a reflection of innovative processes of the development of higher education system. The use of computer technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language is aimed at the formation of a foreign communicative competence. In the modern information society a student in the learning process must not only master knowledge, skills and attainments, but also master new technologies, the ability to self-study and independent work.

The purpose of the study is to demonstrate capabilities and the effectiveness of using the electronic "German-Russian and Russian-German Dictionary of Phraseological Units and Set Phrases" by B.P. Shekasyuk in learning a foreign language in high school, identify the components of the model for the use of computer technologies, including the above-mentioned electronic phraseological dictionary,

The article emphasizes that in foreign language classes at university, the "German-Russian and Russian-German Dictionary of Phraseological Units and Set Phrases" can be used to compile a database of thematic idioms for the phraseological dyads "Work - Idleness", "Wealth - Poverty", "Happiness - Unhappiness", "Truth - Lie", "Intelligence - Stupidity", "Homeland - Foreign Land", etc. for the purpose of using them in monologues (oral and written) and dialogical statements; for translation of texts; to enrich vocabulary by working with vocabulary nests.

As a result of the study, the target, motivational, substantive, procedural and effective components of the model for using an electronic phraseological dictionary in teaching a foreign language at university were identified.

Keywords: university, student, foreign language teaching, electronic phraseological dictionary, phraseological unit, educational technologies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Information technology development affects the education system. Today, the main goal in this area is to improve the educational process, using modern information technologies (Andreeva, Korneva, Kapustina, 2017; 2018; 2019; Khakimzianova, Gubaidullina, Ilyasova, 2018). In the information society, focused on the development of the creative potential of a person, his independence and competitiveness, a student in the learning process must not only master knowledge, skills and achievements, but also master new technologies, the ability to self-study and independent work.

The use of computer technology occupies an important place in teaching a foreign language to a modern student. One of the means of teaching using computer technology is the use of electronic dictionaries. Electronic dictionary is a new word in the history of lexicography. Currently, electronic dictionaries are superior to paper dictionaries and are becoming independent teaching aids. Electronic dictionaries have a number of obvious and significant advantages over traditional dictionaries.

Among special linguistic dictionaries, various phraseological dictionaries are of great interest. These dictionaries contain foreign language parallels to Russian phraseological units, as well as information about the origin of phraseological units, their original motivation, etc. The material of phraseological dictionaries is not words, but phraseological units.

2. DISCUSSION

Electronic dictionaries are an innovation in the field of foreign language teaching methods. In general, developing the ability to competently use lexicographic materials is an integral part of learning a foreign language. The technical capabilities of electronic dictionaries make it possible to add new things to learning.

A modern electronic dictionary can be characterized as a flexible interactive system that provides access to arrays of a wide variety of information that goes far beyond the scope of familiar language knowledge (Kashevarova, 2010).

The use of information technologies in the educational environment, including electronic dictionaries, increases the level of organization of the educational process. It should be noted that this type of work has a number of advantages, such as: ensuring greater convenience and accessibility of the educational and work process, as well as its more efficient organization; quick access to educational information; distance learning; equal access of all students to information and information resources (Polat, 2005).

So, computer technology helps: attract passive listeners; make classes more visual; provide the educational process with new, previously unavailable materials that allow students to demonstrate their creative abilities; to accustom students to work independently with the material; provide instant feedback; increase the intensity of the educational process; cultivate tolerance and sensitivity to the diversity of cultures and spiritual experiences of other peoples; increase the cognitive activity of students, and therefore the desire to study the subject; objectively evaluate the actions of students; accumulate statistical information during the educational process; implement student-centered and differentiated approaches to learning; to discipline the teacher himself, to form his interest in the work; increase the level of development of psychological mechanisms (imagination, attention, memory); activate thought processes (analysis, synthesis, comparison, etc.) (Shishmentseva, 2016).

The use of electronic phraseological dictionaries in foreign language classes is completely justified, since good knowledge of a foreign language is impossible without knowledge of its phraseology. Mastering phraseology makes it easier for a student to read both journalistic, fiction, and economic literature. Reasonable use of phraseological units makes speech more idiomatic. With the help of phraseological expressions that are not translated literally, but are perceived re-interpreted, the aesthetic aspect of the language is enhanced. Phraseologisms play an important role in communication and give different shades to the method of expression: they can make a statement (text) more emotional and expressive, direct aesthetic perception in a certain way, provide certain cultural associations, etc. Very often, phraseological units serve as a kind of code for recognizing the status of the text (the interlocutor, the topic of the statement, the relationship between the participants in communication).

3. RESULTS

The "German-Russian and Russian-German Dictionary of Phraseological Units and Set Phrases" by B.P. Shekasyuk in electronic form Polyglossum allows you to search for more than 140300 words and expressions, as well as their translations in German and Russian. It has the following distinctive features:

- the main body of the dictionary consists of units that have a high level of frequency of use at the present stage of development of the German language;
- the dictionary contains expressions not only of literary and neutral styles, but also high-frequency expressions characteristic of modern German colloquial speech, including those of a reduced stylistic register with possible translation into Russian in the appropriate register; such expressions and phrases were practically not included by domestic dictionary compilers in publications of this type;
- the dictionary contains a certain number of one-word idiomatic formations of the German language, which from the point of view of traditional phraseomatics (according to V.V. Vinogradov) are not classified as such;
- the dictionary contains a significant number of paremiological phrases, which, as a rule, are not recorded at all by bilingual dictionaries;
- the dictionary includes a large number of proverbs and sayings that are often found in modern German speech production and their possible Russian analogues or meaningful correspondences; reference literature on set expressions of this type is currently practically absent;
- most phraseological units are illustrated with conventional examples, taken primarily from modern film and television production, the Internet, as well as from the literature and press of recent decades.

The "German-Russian and Russian-German Dictionary of Phraseological Units and Set Phrases" has the following structure:

1. The dictionary is built on the principle of an alphabetical list of key words and phrases; single-word idioms are ranked in the same order.
2. Construction of a dictionary entry. The title of the article contains the key word of the entire structure. With polysemy, each word is numbered. Following the reference word, phrases are also given in alphabetical order. Each subclause begins with a <*> sign. Variants of individual words in a construction that do not fundamentally change the meaning of the entire phrase as a whole are given in each subarticle with the fraction <Maul/Fresse>. Optional components of the phrase are given in brackets <(gar)>. Synonymous phrases that differ in their composition are given within one subarticle separated by a semicolon <;>. In some cases, a common component for several synonymous vocables is separated from them by a vertical bar <|>. The article ends (if any) with proverbs and sayings, which are separated from the main text of the article by the sign <◇>:

Geld

- ** **Geld machen** ≡ 'делать деньги' o *Er ist ein Lyriker und ist dazu nicht geeignet Geld zu machen.* (Film "Baywatch: Die Rettungsschwimmer von Malibu ")
- *** **Geld für j-n waschen** ≡ 'отмывать чью-л. деньги' o *Rogans Firma wird verdächtigt, Geld für die Mafia zu waschen.* (Filmannonce "Nash Bridges").

<◇>

Geld stinkt nicht. ° Деньги не пахнут o - *Slowakei erhebt auch Ansprüche auf jüdisches Eigentum.* - Klar. Geld stinkt nicht. (Film *Die Wannseekonferenz*) (Шлекасюк, 2006).

3. Translation. A translation or semantic correspondence is provided for each phraseological unit. The purpose of the translation is to reproduce the semantic structure of the German unit as accurately as possible; for this purpose, options are offered that differ in nuances of a stylistic and ethical nature. Each illustrative example is introduced by <◇>. A complete semantic or structural doublet is introduced by the sign <≡>. In cases where in the Russian language there is a close semantic correspondence or phraseological unit with identical functional and stylistic content, it is presented through the similarity sign <≈>. All translation options that are phraseological units or cases of indirect nomination are given in single quotation marks <'очертя голову'>. If the semantics of a translated phraseological unit is opaque, a neutral interpretative

translation is given behind it. Variants of individual words or synonyms are given in the fraction <не видеть/чувствовать опасность>. A common component for several synonymous vocables is separated from them by a vertical bar <|>. In some cases, the national characteristics of German thinking and word usage did not allow us to find Russian correspondences. This applies only to proverbs and sayings. In this case there is no translation (marker <----->):

Land

- * **landaus, landein; landauf, landab** по всей стране
- * **das Land der unbegrenzten Möglichkeiten** эвф. США, Америка
- * **das Land der aufgehenden Sonne** эвф. ≡ 'страна восходящего солнца', Япония
- * **das Land der tausend Seen** эвф. ≡ 'страна тысячи островов', Финляндия
- * **das Land meiner/seiner/usw. Väter** высок. страна предков моих/его/и т.п./Родина/Отчизна
- * **das Land, wo Milch und Honig fließt** библ. волшебная страна с 'молочными реками и кисельными берегами'
- * **das Gelobte/Heilige Land** ≡ 'обетованная земля', Палестина
- * **kein Land mehr sehen** ≈ 'не видать просвета/продыху (от работы/забот)', терять надежду, отчаиваться.

4. The semantic nature of the dictionary led to the reduction of grammatical and spelling comments to a minimum. A grammatical comment appears only to indicate the use of a noun only in singular or plural form <Sg., Pl> and to indicate the dative case of the pronoun <sich [D]>:

- ** **sich [D] den (frischen) Wind um die Nase/die Ohren wehen/ pfeifen lassen** проветриться, пообщаться с кем-л., 'посмотреть/изучить жизнь' о Sie konnten sich nicht bei anderen Menschen ein wenig frischen Wind um die Nase wehen lassen. (H. Fallada "Jeder stirbt für sich allein") .

5. Litters. Since the main body of the vocabulary consists of units of colloquial and neutral vocabulary, there is no need for such marking. The absence of any markings indicates the neutral or neutral-colloquial nature of the expression. When ignorance of the stylistic register can lead to stylistic flaws in use, appropriate marks are given. In some cases, for a more complete understanding of the nature of the use of the expression, notes of an etymological nature or an additional comment are given – <(от злости)>. All expressions and phrases are provided with an empirically determined marker of usage (frequency level) in the form of a set of asterisks from <*> to <****>:

- * **das Land, wo die Zitronen blühen** эвф. Италия (по песне Миньоны из романа Гёте "Вильгельм мастер").

rechnen

- ** **zu rechnen wissen** 'уметь считать деньги', быть экономным
- *** **auf j-n/etw. rechnen** полагаться/рассчитывать на кого-л.

The Polyglossum program uses MS Agent technology to read dictionary text. The user can install the MS Agent character, speaker voices for the desired languages, and the program will be able to pronounce any fragment of the dictionary in the language in which the text is written in the dictionary. This program feature is very important for students studying a foreign language, since, unlike routine work with paper dictionaries, working with the Polyglossum program is interesting and exciting. The program allows you to voice not only fragments of the dictionary, but also any other texts, so several didactic tasks (working with a dictionary, listening) can be solved in parallel.

In foreign language classes at university, the "German-Russian and Russian-German Dictionary of Phraseological Units and Set Phrases" can be used to compile a database of thematic idioms for the phraseological dyads "Work - Idleness", "Wealth - Poverty", "Happiness - Unhappiness", "Truth - Lie", "Intelligence - Stupidity", "Homeland - Foreign Land", etc. for the purpose of using them in monologues (oral and written) and dialogical statements; for translation of texts; to enrich vocabulary by working with vocabulary nests.

To monitor the effectiveness of working with an electronic phraseological dictionary the following types of exercises can be used:

I. JCloze – Filling in the gaps.

Fill in the gaps using the words given:

1. das Land der aufgehenden ;
2. das Land der Seen;
3. das Land meiner .
Väter, tausend, Sonne

II. JMix - mixed-up phrase exercise.

Put the part in order to form a phraseological unit.

1. Zitronen, das, wo, blühen, Land, die;
2. Land, wo, Milch, das, fließt, und, Honig;
3. Land, sehen, mehr, kein.

III. JMatch – Matching the words.

Match the items on the right to the items on the left.

zu rechnen	machen
das Gelobte	wissen
Geld	Land

IV. JQuiz - Quiz (multiple choice answer).

End-of-Module test.

Geld stinkt ...

A. nicht; B sehr; C immer.

The components of the model for using computer technologies, including an electronic phraseological dictionary, in teaching a foreign language are considered: target, motivational, content, procedural and effective.

When designing and implementing the target component of the didactic system, as one of the pedagogical conditions for teaching a foreign language to students, one must remember that without a meaningful goal there is no meaningful action. The goal of teaching a foreign language can be represented in the form of three interrelated goals: 1) the formation of a personality capable of carrying out professional communication in a foreign language; 2) studying a foreign language system and learning to communicate in this language using computer technology; 3) development of the personality of a future specialist capable of integrating into world culture.

The motivational component stimulates the need for knowledge, the development of cognitive and creative activity of students, the desire to learn a language, the desire for professional communication in order to connect their future activities with the use of a foreign language. The motivational sphere of the individual (needs, attitudes, values) underlies any cognitive activity. The learner himself tries to determine the goals of his learning, regulates this process and evaluates its success. The lack of motivation is especially felt when learning a foreign language. Computer learning technologies are the means that create the necessary prerequisites for the emergence of internal motivation.

In the content component, it is advisable to strengthen the practical orientation of the material, highlighting

the essential features of the phenomena being studied, based on the life experience of students. It is important to provide a system of knowledge necessary for the formation of an appropriate level of training for students, a culture of interpersonal communication, where the basis is the ability to demonstrate one's own qualities and abilities, as well as maintain tolerance and respect for the individual characteristics of other people.

The procedural component is a set of methodological support for the material being studied, distant methodological techniques, types and methods of activity using computer technologies, which determine the improvement of the quality of knowledge and skills of students and the development of personality, taking into account individual characteristics.

The effective component assumes the objectivity of learning results, improving the quality of knowledge based on the use of computer technologies and the formation of new skills, abilities, evaluative and creative components of the individual and increasing motivation.

Computer technologies, including the use of the electronic phraseological dictionary, due to their didactic capabilities, can to a certain extent solve all these problems, and therefore, in combination with other forms and methods of teaching, make the process of mastering a foreign language for university students effective and exciting.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The application of information technologies in the educational environment increases the level of organization of the educational process (Konovalenko, 2021). The use of the electronic phraseological dictionary in foreign language classes at university not only has a positive effect on the process of studying phraseological units, but also makes it possible to intensify the activities of students, makes it possible to improve the quality of the pedagogical process, and diversify the forms of interaction between the teacher and students.

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